

Free-electron-driven X-ray caustics from strained van der Waals materials

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Tunable control of X-ray waves remains an open challenge of critical importance for applications in high-resolution X-ray spectroscopy, medical imaging, and radiation therapy. Unlike in the X-ray regime, control over light waves in the visible and IR regimes is ubiquitous in a vast range of applications, and typically relies on widely available optical components. However, analogous optical elements for X-rays are usually inefficient and challenging to fabricate. Here, we propose a method for shaping X-ray waves directly at the source, using the interaction of free electrons with crystalline materials. Specifically, by inducing strain on van der Waals materials, we control their interaction with free electrons in a manner that tunes the emissions of the X-rays and forms caustic X-ray beams. The development of wave-shaping concepts like caustics generation in the X-ray spectral range could benefit from achievements in this field in the optical range and may help bypass the noted limits of current X-ray optics technology. Looking forward, shaping the interference of X-rays at the atomic scale could enable further developments in high-resolution X-ray science. © 2023 Optica Publishing Group under the terms of the [Optica Open Access Publishing Agreement](#)

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1. INTRODUCTION

van der Waals (vdW) structures, which are composed of multi-layered 2D materials held together by weak vdW forces, are often subject to various kinds of out-of-plane deformations such as folds [1,2], scrolls [3], bubbles [4–8], ripples [9–12], buckles [13,14], crumples [15], and tents [8,16]. There has been a recent surge of interest in these deformations and their physical effects in topics ranging from precision strain control [11,17,18] to strain-induced novel phenomena [19–22]. In particular, strain engineering has emerged as a promising means to manipulate and enhance light emission from transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) and transition metal thiophosphates [23]. However, the use of strain engineering in light emission has thus far been confined to the optical regime (\sim eV photon energy), restricted by the optical bandgap of vdW materials [24]. This limitation raises the question of whether strain engineering can be used to manipulate and enhance light emission at much higher photon energies including X-rays.

The question of how to control and enhance light in the X-ray regime is especially pertinent given the challenge in shaping X-rays by traditional optical elements. Traditional elements in X-ray optics include crystals for Bragg reflection [25–27], zone plates with high aspect ratios [28–30], and compound optics [31]. However, most X-ray optics is inefficient or very complicated to create. Furthermore, traditional schemes that use high-quality

X-ray optics generally require coherent X-ray light with substantial photon flux, as is only available in large facilities, such as free-electron lasers [32]. These challenges limit much of the innovation and promise of X-ray optics, particularly in the development of more compact systems that offer portability and enhanced control over the nanoscale properties of the generated radiation.

Shaping X-ray waves [33–36] is not as widely used as light shaping in the optics community. Consequently, the breakthroughs of beam shaping in optics have not made an equivalent impact in X-ray science. An example of potential interest is the Airy beam [37–39], a nondiffracting form of light propagation that often manifests itself with a curved trajectory and asymmetric extended side lobes [40]. The unique properties of this type of beam has attracted great interest from both fundamental [40–43] and applied [39,44,45] perspectives. An intriguing application of Airy beams is high-contrast, large field-of-view (FOV) light-sheet imaging [46–48], which benefits from the narrow intensity distribution and relatively long nondiffracting axial extent of such beams. In addition, the self-healing property of Airy beams helps the waves propagate in turbulent conditions [39,49], such as organic compounds and biological specimens in their natural aqueous environment [50]. Looking at the bigger picture, an Airy beam is just one example of caustics, which are universal phenomena emerging in wave systems in nature. Although the concept of caustics has had huge impact on the wider field of optics over the

past decades [39,51], this concept has not had a similar impact in X-ray science. Only a few pioneering experiments realized X-ray caustics [52,53], and these were still quite limited, especially when aiming to nanoscale dimensions. This discussion illustrates how, despite the variety of optical elements available to focus and steer X-rays [27,28], they are still much more limited than in the optical regime, especially for beam shaping.

In this paper, we propose bending crystalline structures, which model the curvature generated in certain strained vdW materials, as an effective means to shape X-ray emission. We specifically highlight the advantages of strain engineering in vdW materials to create bending films with radii on the scale of micrometers. We find that X-rays produced by free electrons interacting with bent vdW materials can be shaped into caustics. Importantly, vdW materials can be bent to large curvatures beyond the capability of traditional 3D crystals; for example, by coaxially stacking vdW nanotubes [54] and by rolling up 2D layers [55]. Furthermore, we show that X-ray caustics in the form of Airy beams can be tuned in focal length, diffraction-free range, and wavelength by varying the vdW material strain geometry and the electron energy. Our study also reveals that the formation of Airy beams is limited by the quantum uncertainty of the electron itself. Specifically, the coherent momentum range of the incident electron alters the caustic and provides an additional degree of freedom to control it by electron wavepacket shaping [56–61]. The effect of crystal bending on the spectrum of both bremsstrahlung and channeling radiation has been investigated [62–64]. However, the effect of crystal bending on the emitted beam profile associated with these or any other processes has not been explored, except the focusing of X-rays from ultrarelativistic channeled particles moving along a long, bent crystal with a very small curvature [65]. We thus introduce strain and bending as the means to control the interference of X-ray waves, focus them, and create X-ray caustics of nanoscale dimensions.

Our results show focusing of X-rays at very short distances (down to several micrometers) in comparison to most traditional approaches in X-ray optics and most large-scale facilities [26,66–68], which usually rely on bulkier optical elements and longer distances. The shorter focal lengths enable larger numerical apertures (NAs) and avoid various channels of absorption and scattering, especially in softer X-rays that are also absorbed by air. Our results pave the way to the development of versatile, compact X-ray sources capable of directly shaping emitted X-rays into nanobeams. Such nanobeams could mitigate the need for subsequent optical components in high-NA applications. In particular, the realization of an X-ray Airy beam could be useful in high-resolution imaging and material characterization applications (e.g., nano-ARPES [34,35]), exploiting the generation of light sheets that can probe selected slices of a target specimen.

2. SETUP

Free-electron-driven X-ray emission from vdW materials can arise from two coherent processes: parametric X-ray radiation (PXR) and coherent bremsstrahlung (CBS). PXR was first realized experimentally in 1985 and features high radiation intensity in a narrow spectral interval [69]. vdW materials were demonstrated as controllable platforms to study these phenomena, serving as structures to generate relatively monochromatic, high-brightness X-rays, whose frequency can be tuned by controlling the electron energy and material design [70]. Our concept of creating X-ray caustics applies to both mechanisms because the X-ray emission

Fig. 1. Illustration of an Airy beam created from a cylindrically bent multilayer structure. We use ray optics to compare the monochromatic X-ray emission produced by a free electron passing through (a) flat and (b) cylindrically bent multilayer structures. The emission direction is tunable as a function of the electron incidence angle θ and velocity \mathbf{v} , as well as the orientation of the crystal reciprocal lattice vectors (g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp}) and film bending radius. A collimated X-ray beam can be excited from a flat multilayer structure, as shown in (a). In comparison, when the structure is bent, the electron incidence angle θ varies along the electron trajectory, so the rays emerging from different atomic layers are not parallel and may converge along a caustic line, generating an X-ray Airy beam, as shown in (b). The figures are not to scale.

in PXR and CBS follows the same dispersion relation. In particular, PXR [69] is emitted from polarization currents induced by the incident electrons on the bound electrons of the material. In contrast, CBS [69] is emitted from the wiggling of the incident-electron trajectories because of a periodic series of bremsstrahlung interactions with the nuclei and bound electrons in the material, where each interaction produces some acceleration of an incident electron and causes it to emit radiation. The contribution of PXR to the radiation peak is comparable to that from CBS for slightly relativistic electrons [71], and usually dominant for ultrarelativistic electrons [69,72,73]. Consequently, we focus on the PXR process to demonstrate the concept in our simulations below, but the conclusions apply to both emission mechanisms.

We use WSe₂ as the example of a platform to study PXR induced by free electrons interacting with strained vdW materials. PXR can be modeled by treating the periodic atomic structure as a discrete dipole array, with bound electrons around each atom being encapsulated in an effective dipole quantified through an associated X-ray atomic polarizability [73,74]. We consider a cylindrically bent multilayer vdW material structure produced by out-of-plane strain [17,18] as shown in Fig. 1(b), with the cylinder axis along the y direction.

Although strain can in-principle be applied to any type of crystalline material to achieve X-ray caustics, vdW materials provide a unique set of advantages for the design of on-demand X-ray caustic patterns. For one thing, vdW materials can be bent to large

curvatures (small radii) beyond the capability of traditional crystals through different methods; for example, by coaxially stacking vdW nanotubes [54] and by rolling up 2D layers [55]. Large curvatures are important for strong focusing and short focal distances. Indeed, the examples we show below rely on bending radii of several micrometers to present focal distances of 5 μm ; thus, we use the bent vdW material WSe₂. We note that the same approach directly applies to any crystalline material.

We consider two crystal deformation mechanisms associated with bending crystalline materials: elastic and plastic bendings [17,18,75]. In elastic bending, the entire material slab bends as a single plate, with a behavior that follows continuum mechanics plate theory. Characterized by a length-invariant neutral surface, the crystal layers are extended or compressed along the direction normal to such surfaces, in proportion to the distance [44]. In plastic bending, each layer bends independently, locally maintaining in-plane atomic distances and interlayer separations nearly intact via shearing and slipping [17,18]. For the case of vdW materials, recent experimental results show that their bending involves both types of mechanisms, although with a dominant contribution by plastic bending, because the 2D layers are held together by relatively weak vdW forces [17,18]. We therefore assume plastic bending in the examples below and consider invariant lattice constants. Incidentally, no significant differences are found when instead considering elastic bending with in-plane extension and compression taken into consideration (Supplement 1, Section 5).

3. RESULTS

When an electron is normally impinging on the WSe₂ multilayer structure shown in Fig. 1(a), the emitted photons interfere coherently following dispersion relations that are determined by the reciprocal lattice vectors of the crystal [70,71]:

$$\frac{\omega}{v} = \frac{\omega}{c} \cos \varphi + g_{\perp} \cos \theta - g_{\parallel} \sin \theta, \quad (1)$$

where ω is the angular photon frequency; c and v are the free-space light and electron velocities, respectively; g_{\perp} and g_{\parallel} are the out-of-plane and in-plane components of the crystal reciprocal lattice vector, respectively; and φ and θ are the photon emission and the electron incidence angles, respectively. A monochromatic collimated X-ray beam is then generated from the flat multilayer structure, as shown in Fig. 1(a), where some of the elements of Eq. (1) are indicated. Therefore, the collimated X-ray beam can be tuned by varying the emission angle, crystal lattice constant, electron velocity, and electron incidence angle [70]. It is noteworthy that the general form of the Smith–Purcell radiation, including a conical diffraction effect [76,77], can be derived by eliminating the in-plane reciprocal lattice vector g_{\parallel} .

The X-ray beam can be further manipulated by gradually varying the angle θ between the electron and the stacked crystal layers, which can be achieved by using a curved multilayer structure. We consider a cylindrically bent multilayer structure as shown in Fig. 1(b) to demonstrate the paradigm. This approach can be easily extended to other curved structures provided that the curvature of each layer can be carefully defined. The incidence angle θ in Fig. 1(b) decreases as the radius of curvature increases along the electron trajectory in the z direction. Therefore, photons scattered by certain reciprocal lattice vectors (g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp}), such as $g_{\parallel} = 0$ with $g_{\perp} > 0$, would converge. A full-wave simulation confirms that X-ray caustics are created at the convergence area. The most

striking feature of the caustic is highlighted by the dashed blue line in Fig. 1(b), marking an abrupt change in intensity known as a catastrophe (specifically a “fold catastrophe”) [42] in the present instance. The optical fold catastrophe is always accompanied by an Airy beam pattern around the caustic line, which features a curved profile and asymmetric extended side lobes.

To exemplify the general concept in Fig. 1, we apply it to the PXR excited by a 1 MeV free electron passing through a WSe₂ multilayer structure with a thickness of $T = 300$ nm. The radiation pattern can be obtained by adding together the electric field scattered by each layer. Figure 2 compares the X-ray intensity pattern from a flat [Fig. 2(a)] and a bent [Fig. 2(b)] WSe₂ multilayer structure in the emission angle region $\varphi = 80^{\circ} - 93^{\circ}$ at distances $\rho = 3.5 - 6.0$ μm to the middle point of intersection between the electron and the atomic crystal layers. In Fig. 2(a), we set the electron incidence angle to $\theta = \sin^{-1}(4/5)$ to compare it to the configuration portrayed in Fig. 2(b), where the electron passes through a bent crystal. The collimated X-ray beam propagates at an angle $\varphi = 86.6^{\circ}$, matching the X-ray dispersion in Eq. (1). In Fig. 2(b), we set the crystal bending radius to $R = 5$ μm and the electron trajectory displacement relative to the bending axis to $L = 4$ μm . The bending radii of the layers lie in the $R - T/2$ to $R + T/2$ range. An Airy beam with a spot size ~ 10 nm is generated at a distance $\rho \approx 4.8$ μm . We build the ρ - s frames by rotating the $x - z$ frames anticlockwise by angles of 3.4° [Fig. 2(a)] and 6.2° [Fig. 2(b)], so that ρ and s represent the axial and transverse directions of the collimated X-ray beam, respectively. The electric field profiles are plotted in the transverse cross-section planes ($y - s$) and the longitudinal plane ($\rho - s$). The latter is not to scale to make the Airy beam profile clearer. Detailed calculation procedures are given in Section 6 (Methods).

We now describe the radiation produced by electrons traversing the bent structure. Each bent layer is approximated by a flat layer whose position, normal vector, and 2D crystal structure are determined by those at the point where the electron intersects it. This model is accurate under the conditions here considered, in which the evanescent field carried by the electron decays within a small distance compared to the bending radius. We then treat the contribution of each layer to the emission through the dispersion relation (Supplement 1, Section 2)

$$\frac{\omega}{v} = \frac{\omega}{c} \cos \varphi + g_{\perp} \cos \theta - g_{\parallel} \sin \theta + g_{\parallel} \theta \cos \theta, \quad (2)$$

modified from Eq. (1) by the additional term $g_{\parallel} \theta \cos \theta$ to capture the relative layer shifts. In particular, the electron incidence angle varies in the range $\theta = \sin^{-1}[L/(R - T/2)] - \sin^{-1}[L/(R + T/2)]$ in Fig. 2(b), and correspondingly, the photon emission angle φ varies along the electron trajectory as illustrated in Fig. 1(b). The numerical results show that photons scattered by the reciprocal lattice vector ($g_{\parallel} = 0$, $g_{\perp} = 5 \times 2\pi/d$), where $d = 12.98$ \AA is the interlayer distance of the {001} planes in bulk WSe₂, are mainly responsible for the formation of an Airy beam, as shown in Fig. 2(b). The central point of such beam subtends an angle $\varphi_c = 83.8^{\circ}$ with respect to the electron trajectory. The bottom inset of Fig. 2(b) shows an enlarged image of the Airy beam, which remains diffraction-free over the $\rho = 4.3 - 5.3$ μm range (see next paragraph and Supplement 1, Section 3). The top insets depict the electric field intensity profile across several transverse planes, with the extremal values $\rho = 4.2$ μm and 5.4 μm chosen outside the Airy beam diffraction-free region. The Airy beam

Fig. 2. Caustic X-ray beam from a bent multilayer WSe_2 heterostructure. We compare the X-ray intensity profiles of (b) a caustic X-ray beam and (a) a collimated X-ray beam. The X-ray emission from the bent WSe_2 heterostructure in (b) forms an Airy beam with a spot size of ~ 10 nm that remains diffraction-free over a propagation length of ~ 1 μm ($\rho = 4.3\text{--}5.3$ μm). The ρ – s axes denote the rotated frame from the x – z axes by angles of (a) 3.4° and (b) 6.2° , with the ρ axis pointing along the emission direction. The radius of curvature of the WSe_2 heterostructure is $R = 5$ μm . The axis of the bending cylinder is shifted by $L = 4$ μm from the electron trajectory. (a) and (b) share the same color scale, sample thickness (300 nm), electron kinetic energy (1 MeV), and photon energy (3 keV).

width determined from Fig. 2(b) (~ 10 nm) is much smaller than the width (~ 0.5 μm) of the collimated X-ray beam in Fig. 2(a).

The trajectory equation of the Airy beam (i.e., the envelope equation) can be obtained by combining Eq. (2) and its derivative with respect to θ (see detailed derivation in Supplement 1, Section 3). The axial distribution of the caustic profile yields

$$\rho(r_c) = \frac{\omega}{c g_{\perp}} \frac{R^3}{L^2} \sin^2 \varphi_0 + 3 \left(-\frac{\cos \varphi_0}{\cos \theta_0} - \frac{\omega}{c g_{\perp}} \frac{\sin^2 \varphi_0}{\sin^2 \theta_0} \right) r_c, \quad (3)$$

under the condition $T \ll R$ (small multilayer thickness compared to the bending radius), and where $\cos \varphi_0 = \frac{1}{\beta} + \frac{g_{\perp}}{k} \cos \theta_0$, $\sin \theta_0 = \frac{L}{R}$, and $r_c = -\frac{T}{2} - \frac{T}{2}$ is the radial distance of the different layers from the central layer. The first term $\frac{\omega}{c g_{\perp}} \frac{R^3}{L^2} \sin^2 \varphi_0$ can be interpreted as the focal length, where the center of the Airy beam caustics appears relative to the origin. In Fig. 3(b), colored solid curves represent the focal length, shown as a function of bending radius R and the L/R ratio. The second term in Eq. (3) is the axial distribution of the Airy beam. Colored dashed curves in Fig. 3(b) represent the axial caustic length, which scale linearly with the thickness T under the assumed condition $T \ll R$. The results in Fig. 3(b) agree with the ray optics analysis and show that the Airy beam displays a longer axial spatial extent and is farther from the source with a smaller L/R ratio. Focal lengths up to centimeters can be achieved by increasing the bending radius, the sample thickness and, correspondingly, the electron energy (Supplement 1, Section 6).

Optical diffraction can, however, produce a degradation in the formation of an Airy beam that is not captured by ray optics analyses. To study such effect, we adopt optical diffraction theory for lenses (the Airy beam can be treated as lensing with aberrations) and analyze the Airy beam that it predicts. The focal depth [78], defined as the axial extent of the focal region, scales inversely proportional to the NA squared. We find the expression $\frac{2\lambda f^2}{7^2 \sin^2 \varphi_0}$ for the focal depth, where λ is the wavelength, f is the focal length [first term in Eq. (3)], and $T \sin \varphi_0$ is the effective length of the source. To have a distinct focal spot, the axial extent should be much smaller than the focal length (i.e., $\frac{2\lambda f^2}{\sin^2 \varphi_0 T^2} / f \ll 1$); otherwise the focal region extends all the way from the source to the focal spot, so that the latter is completely blurred and indistinguishable from the background. Indeed, the ratio between the focal depth and the focal length, plotted in Fig. 3(c), shows that both a larger L/R ratio and a larger interaction length favor a distinct focal spot for the Airy beam. The optimal choice of L/R for a given application therefore involves a trade-off between a longer axial extent (favored by a smaller L/R ratio) and a more distinct focal spot (favored by a larger L/R ratio).

Fig. 3. Analysis of the generated X-ray Airy beam: quantifying its focal length, axial caustic length, and conditions for its formation. (a) Focal length and the axial caustic length. The image is not to scale, as the focal length is much larger than the axial caustic length. (b) Focal (left vertical axis) and axial caustic length (right vertical axis) as a function of the L/R ratio (see Fig. 2). The axial caustic length scales linearly with the thickness T (colored dashed curves), while the focal length changes when varying the bending radius R (colored solid curves), under the condition $T \ll R$. (c) Regime in which an X-ray caustic can develop. Its formation is limited by wave diffraction, which sets a finite (nonzero) focal depth. The latter must be smaller than the focal length for a meaningful caustic to emerge. The ratio of focal depth to focal length is shown as the vertical axis. The regime in which caustics can (cannot) form is highlighted by a blue (red) background. The ratio is a function of bending radius R , thickness T , and L/R ratio. The electron kinetic energy is 1 MeV and the photon energy is 3 keV.

Fig. 4. Tunability of X-ray caustics and their prospects for light-sheet applications: comparing two X-ray caustics with different parameters. (a) Caustic generated with stronger crystal bending ($L = 4.0 \mu\text{m}$), which creates a smaller Airy beam spot size, coming at the price of a shorter axial caustic length. (b) Caustic produced with weaker crystal bending ($L = 2.5 \mu\text{m}$), which results in a larger Airy beam spot size, achieving a longer axial caustic length. These examples emphasize the potential of using X-ray caustics for light-sheet X-ray microscopy. The color scales in (a) and (b) are normalized to their own maximum values. Other parameters are the same as in Fig. 2(b).

An intriguing application of the Airy beam is light-sheet imaging. Two key parameters in light-sheet microscopy are the field of view and the resolution, which are connected to the diffraction-free range and beam width of the Airy beam. The diffraction-free range can be approximated by the axial caustic length, as plotted in Fig. 3(b), which is a function of L/R and the thickness T . In Fig. 4, we compare the Airy beams produced by choosing different shifts of the electron trajectory $L = 4 \mu\text{m}$ [Fig. 4(a)] and $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ [Fig. 4(b)] while keeping other parameters the same as in Fig. 2(b). The $\rho - s$ axes denote the anticlockwise rotated frame from the $x - z$ axes by angles of (a) 6.2° and (b) 18.4° , with the ρ axis oriented along the emission direction. Figure 4(a) shows a smaller Airy beam spot size, coming at the price of a shorter axial caustic length [$\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$, Fig. 3(b)]. In contrast, Fig. 4(b) shows a bigger Airy beam spot size, but achieving a longer axial caustic length [$\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$; see also Fig. 3(b)].

Electron beams diverge due to the space charge effect and multiple scattering inside the crystal. To investigate the feasibility of our scheme under these limitations, we studied the robustness of the Airy beam against electron beam divergence. In Fig. 5(b) we compared the Airy beam width for incident electron beams (e-beams) with different spot sizes and divergence angles. Typically,

the sample is at the focal plane of the electron beam. We chose three different locations ($\rho = 10.5 \mu\text{m}$, $11.3 \mu\text{m}$, and $12.1 \mu\text{m}$) in Fig. 4(b) and plotted the transverse intensity profiles in Fig. 5(b). The e-beam follows a Gaussian electron density distribution with an rms divergence angle $\delta\theta$ and an rms spot size δr . The left, middle, and right columns are the results obtained, respectively, from an ideal point electron, an e-beam with divergence angle $\delta\theta$, and an e-beam with spot size δr . The comparison shows that the width of the Airy beams can be broadened but maintains its basic features within the caustic region. More information on the electron beam divergence can be found in Supplement 1, Section 6.

We then compared the beam widths for the collimated X-ray beam and the light-sheet X-ray beam by plotting the transverse intensity profiles in Fig. 5(c). The left, middle, and right columns show results obtained, respectively, from an ideal point electron, an e-beam with divergence angle $\delta\theta$, and an e-beam with spot size δr . These plots show that the light-sheet X-ray beam still has a smaller beam width than the collimated one, even when created by e-beams with finite divergence angles and spot sizes.

We calculated the flux density at the focal point, which is at $\rho = 10.9 \mu\text{m}$ in Fig. 4(b). The e-beam that interacts with the vdW material has a Gaussian profile, a current of $100 \mu\text{A}$, energy of 1 MeV , an rms divergence angle of 25 mrad , and a spot size of 19 nm . The parameters are chosen considering the space charge effect and multiple electron scatterings by the crystal (Supplement 1, Section 7). The peak flux density is about $10^{10} \text{ photons/sec/mm}^2/0.1\% \text{ BW}$, which is comparable to the density of a focused beam created by a polycapillary lens with a state-of-the-art X-ray tube [79]. However, the latter suffers from large spot sizes and broadband frequency ranges due to the incoherent nature of compact X-ray sources [80,81] (Supplement 1, Section 14).

Note that related schemes for beam shaping of free-electron radiation were proposed for radiation in the microwave [82–84], terahertz [85], and optical [86,87] regimes, but so far not for the X-ray regime. These proposed schemes use custom aperiodic gratings for a Smith–Purcell-type effect [88,89]. The most common proposal, which was also recently demonstrated experimentally in the optical regime [87], relied on a grating with a chirp. Our study can be seen as a complementary scheme where the gratings are realized on the subnanometer scale using a crystalline atomic periodicity rather than a grating, and chirp is realized by the bending. However, note that strain and bending are not equivalent to

Fig. 5. Effect of the electron beam parameters on the quality of the generated X-ray caustics. We test the robustness of the X-ray caustic concept by studying its dependence on various (Gaussian) electron beam parameters (divergence angle $\delta\theta$ and spot size δr), defined in (a) from the rms divergence angle and spot size, respectively. (b) Comparison of the Airy beam width at three caustic locations (see color labels). The left column shows the intensity profile from an ideal point electron (zero divergence angle and spot size). The middle (right) column shows the effect of a finite divergence angle (spot size). (c) Comparison of the width of the X-ray Airy beam (solid curves) and the collimated X-ray beam (dashed curves) at $\rho = 11.3 \mu\text{m}$. The left column shows results from an ideal point electron. The setup is the same as in Fig. 2, except that the electron incidence angle is $\theta = \sin^{-1}(1/2)$ in the flat multilayer structure, and the electron trajectory shift is $L = 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ in the bent multilayer structure. The s axis is defined by rotating the x axis clockwise by angles of 18.4° and 23.1° for the Airy beams and the collimated beams, respectively.

the chirping of a grating. A fundamental difference between these schemes and our work arises from the fact that electrons in PXR penetrate through the sample instead of passing by its surface. This different configuration, which causes each electron to interact with many different atomic layers, inspires designs based on the use of curved structures. A similar approach could be adopted in other spectral regimes; for example, suggesting the creation of caustic beams in the terahertz range by bent Smith–Purcell structures driven by free electrons. Note that passing by the grating surface, as in Smith–Purcell radiation, prevents the electron from undergoing multiple scattering by atoms inside the materials and increases the electron propagation distance. However, it requires ultrarelativistic electrons to emit high-frequency photons, considering the electron Bohr cutoff $L_{\text{Bohr}} = v\gamma/\omega$ [90], where v is the electron velocity, γ is the Lorentz factor, and ω is the photon frequency.

4. QUANTUM PARAMETRIC X-RAY RADIATION (QPXR): CORRECTIONS AND LIMITATIONS DUE TO THE ELECTRON QUANTUM WAVE NATURE

To better understand the limitations on electron radiation introduced by the quantum nature of the electrons and photons under consideration, it is beneficial to compare our mechanisms of X-ray radiation to the simpler scenario of Cherenkov radiation (CR). There, conservation of momentum causes the free electron to recoil when emitting a photon. Consequently, the coherence of CR and its ability to form a short shock wave are bounded by the momentum uncertainty of the incident electrons [60]. In contrast, the conservation of momentum in PXR and CBS involves both the crystal and the electron [69], so part of the recoil is absorbed by the crystal and not only by the electron. Therefore, the coherence of the X-ray emission is bounded by the combination of uncertainties in the electron coherent momentum and in the crystal reciprocal lattice vectors. Figure 6(a) shows that the gradual change in the crystal reciprocal lattice vectors helps maintain the interference required to create the caustic almost independently of the coherence of the longitudinal momentum of the incident electron. Figure 6(b) presents the estimated coherence of the electron transverse momentum required for the formation of the X-ray caustics. Electron transverse momentum in the keV/c range can be obtained by focusing the electron beam to a small spot, which can reach subnanometer sizes in electron microscopes [91].

In a complementary picture, a first-principles, rigorous quantum-mechanical treatment of any excitation (including X-ray photons) generated by an electron beam with small incident-divergence and transmitted-scattering angles shows that the result is fully equivalent to the coherent excitation produced by a line dipole (with wave vector ω/v), averaged incoherently (i.e., summing intensities) over the transverse beam directions, with position-dependent weights taken from the electron intensity distribution across the e-beam [58]. In the point-electron limit, only one such line dipole is present, thereby producing maximum coherence in the emission. As the lateral size of the e-beam increases, the generated caustics is blurred by incoherent averaging over the emission of more separated line dipoles.

5. DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK

We next propose a path toward the experimental measurement of our proposal. One can use the knife-edge scanning technique

Fig. 6. Limitations due to quantum effects on the formation of X-ray beams: the role of electron coherence. (a) Analysis of the role of electron coherence and the variation of the reciprocal lattice vectors in the generation of caustics. Constrained by the conservation of energy and momentum, coherent photons are entangled with the corresponding electron final state (\mathbf{p}' or \mathbf{p}'_1) from electron initial states of the same energy. The black dashed curves represent electron isoenergy contours. The red-yellow lines indicate the combination of photon momenta and reciprocal lattice vectors. Coherence from the initial momentum distribution of the electron (denoted by the purple ellipse) is transferred to the photons via the connected red-yellow lines. For relativistic electrons, the curvatures of the black dashed curves are small, making them almost flat near the p_z axis. Therefore, the quantum coherence of the electron is limited only in the transverse directions. The right inset is a diagrammatic representation of PXR, where \mathbf{p} , \mathbf{p}' , \mathbf{k} , and \mathbf{g} denote, respectively, the momenta of the initial electron, the final electron, the photon, and the reciprocal lattice vector. (b) Representation of the required electron coherence (in the p_x momentum component) for the Airy beam to be created with full coherence, shown for different sample radii, thicknesses, and L/R ratios.

[79,92], as already applied to characterize the X-ray beam in nanofocusing lensing experiments [66,68]. The same technique can reconstruct the entire 3D profile of the X-ray Airy beam. Specifically, a nanosized metal film (e.g., Rh or Pb film), can serve as the knife edge, and scan through the Airy beam region with nanometer-sized steps. In addition, a micron-sized pinhole or slot [93] should be placed between the vdW crystal source and the detector, to isolate the monochromatic X-ray Airy beam from X-ray emission by core-electron transitions, bremsstrahlung, and PXR emission to other wavelengths and other orders. Such a pinhole or slot will also serve to block the secondary and large angle scattered electrons. The emitted X-rays can be captured by an energy-dispersive spectrometer to further filter the target wavelength from noise (Supplement 1, Section 10). Compared to the previous nanofocusing lensing experiments [66,68], the challenge in our scheme lies in integrating the knife-edge scanning technique with an electron microscope, electron diffraction setup, or another high-quality (directional) e-beam source, as necessary for the PXR mechanism [70].

Regarding the choice of crystal for the experiment—a vdW material or otherwise—note that the required material should have a controllable and flexible crystalline structure on the atomic scale [17,18,50]. Most vdW materials are good candidates for this purpose because they can also be made atomically flat relatively easily [94]. Furthermore, the wide variety of vdW materials and the ability to form them into heterostructures [95–97] make them customizable on the atomic scale. This degree-of-freedom is especially important given the reliance of our concept on angstrom-scale precision. Another important point is the robustness of the material, especially to radiation damage, where certain vdW materials were already tested [98,99]. Many vdW materials also benefit from high in-plane thermal conductivity [100,101] and carrier mobility [102,103], which is good for heat dissipation and charge dissipation and supports operation at high X-ray flux.

In conclusion, we propose a paradigm to generate X-ray caustics from free electrons traversing bent crystal structures. Our work anticipates the application of light-sheet imaging in the X-ray regime. The generation of X-ray caustics is integrated as an intrinsic feature of the X-ray source, eliminating the need for X-ray lenses or masks, which are lossy or nonexistent in the X-ray regime. The diffraction-free length and other characteristics of the so-produced Airy beams can be adjusted by tuning the parameters of the incident electron and crystal bending. The analysis of quantum aspects in the generation process shows that entanglement of post-emission electron states and photon states can prevent caustic generation unless the transverse coherent momentum of the electron is properly prepared.

The findings of this work are not limited to cylindrical bending, which approximates any general 2D bending for small thicknesses, if the radius of curvature changes monotonously along the electron trajectory. More general variations of curvature in 3D can be included in Eq. (2) through the functional dependence of the incidence angle θ .

As discussed in this work, for a slightly to moderately relativistic electron, only the local curvature of the shaped vdW materials contributes to the X-ray beam shaping. In contrast, ultrarelativistic electrons provide much broader excitation [104]; therefore, the curvature over a larger area of the bent vdW material plays a role in their induced X-ray beam shaping. In addition, the dynamical effect (i.e., multiple diffractions of X-rays at crystal planes) plays an essential role in the excitation of PXR for ultrarelativistic electrons [105]. More complex structured and highly monochromatic X-ray beams can be produced following this concept.

Another interesting possibility is the dynamical control over the produced Airy beams by relying on real-time modulation of the material strain, which can be achieved by applying acoustic waves [106] or by introducing pressure differences above and below the multilayer crystal [4,17].

6. METHODS

A. Scattering Field of an Electron by a Single Flat Crystal Layer

Consider a crystal layer with Bravais lattice spanning the x - y plane at $z = 0$. We use electric dipoles to model the bound electrons at discrete lattice points $\mathbf{R} = m\mathbf{a}_1 + n\mathbf{a}_2 + \mathbf{R}_a$, where $\mathbf{R} = (x, y)$, \mathbf{a}_1 and \mathbf{a}_2 are 2D primitive vectors, m and n are integers, and $\mathbf{r}_a = (\mathbf{R}_a, 0)$ is the position of a reference atom relative to the center of the 2D unit cell. An electron of velocity \mathbf{v} penetrates the crystal layer at a position $\mathbf{r}_c = (\mathbf{R}_c, 0)$, with incidence angle θ relative to the plane normal. The scattering field produced by the interaction of the free electron with the crystal layer can be decomposed into contributions associated with different in-plane reciprocal lattice vectors \mathbf{g}_\parallel as

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{g}_\parallel, \mathbf{r}, \omega) = \frac{i\epsilon\alpha(\omega)}{A\epsilon_0^2 v_z} \frac{e^{ikr' + i\mathbf{g}_\parallel \cdot (\mathbf{R}_a - \mathbf{R}_c)}}{4\pi r'} \frac{(k^2 - \mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}) \cdot (k\boldsymbol{\beta} - \boldsymbol{\kappa})}{k^2 - \kappa^2}, \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha(\omega)$ is the atomic polarizability, A is the unit cell area, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, v_z is the z component of electron velocity \mathbf{v} , $r' = |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_c|$ is the distance to the impact point of the electron, $k = \omega/c$ is the light wavenumber in vacuum, $\mathbf{k} = k(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_c)/r'$, $\boldsymbol{\beta} = \mathbf{v}/c$, c is the light speed in vacuum,

$\boldsymbol{\kappa} = (\mathbf{k}_\parallel + \mathbf{g}_\parallel) + \frac{\omega - (\mathbf{k}_\parallel + \mathbf{g}_\parallel) \cdot \mathbf{v}}{v_z} \hat{z}$, and \mathbf{k}_\parallel is the x - y component of \mathbf{k} (see Supplement 1, Section 1).

The final scattering field is the coherent summation of the fields represented by Eq. (1), arising from different layers for a common \mathbf{g}_\parallel . However, the contributions from different in-plane reciprocal lattice vectors are summed incoherently because they contribute to different caustics (i.e., the incoherent average over the electron impact position \mathbf{R}_c results in the incoherent summation over \mathbf{g}_\parallel). The strongest Airy beam shown in Fig. 2 comes from $\mathbf{g}_\parallel = 0$.

Note that we neglect the susceptibility of the medium in simulating the propagation of the X-rays, which is represented by Eqs. (1) and (2). The susceptibility of a medium in the X-ray regime is on the order of $10^{-4} - 10^{-5}$; therefore, it is generally negligible, except at grazing incidence [27,74]. However, it influences the phases of the waves at the caustics, which result from the constructive interference of emitted waves. We estimate the maximum phase difference of the waves, with and without the average susceptibility of the medium included, through $\Delta\varphi = \frac{\omega}{c} |\chi| T \approx 1.6 < \pi$ using the parameters in Fig. 2, where χ is the average susceptibility [74]. The correction to the caustic positions induced by Eq. (2) is less than one wavelength, which is 4 Å for 3 keV photons. Therefore, we concluded that it is reasonable to neglect the susceptibility.

The approach to calculate the total radiation by summing the fields scattered by multiple layers is generally known as the kinematic theory. It neglects multiple reflections of photons produced by Bragg scattering, whose inclusion leads to what is known as dynamical theory [74]. However, a dynamical theory in curved structures with large curvatures has not, to the best of our knowledge, been explored. In addition, the dynamical effects are resonant and appear within narrow bandwidths and specific directions [74]. Therefore, we conclude that our scheme of shaping X-rays based on kinematic theory applies to most general cases.

B. Replacing Bent Layers with Flat Layers

Consider a 1 MeV free electron penetrating the cylindrically bent WSe₂ structure shown in Fig. 2(b). In the calculation, we replace the bent layers with flat layers, which are tangent to the former ones at the electron impact points. Importantly, we model the flat layers so that the atom positions match those in the bent layers near the electron impact points. Details can be found in Supplement 1, Section 2. This approximation is justified by examining the Bohr cutoff [90] $v\gamma/\omega$ (γ is the Lorentz contraction factor and ω is the angular frequency of the electron field), which gives the characteristic distance for the exponential decay of the evanescent electromagnetic field that accompanies the free electron in vacuum. In our case, this distance is smaller than the dimension of one unit cell (0.18 nm for a 1 MeV electron and 3 keV photons). The range of electron kinetic energies that accommodates this approximation is discussed in Supplement 1, Section 4.

C. Limitations Due to Quantum Effects

The initial electron-photon state is described as a superposition of electron momentum states $|\mathbf{p}\rangle$ as $|i\rangle = \sum_{\mathbf{p}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{V}} \psi(\mathbf{p}) |\mathbf{p}\rangle \otimes |0\rangle$, where V is the quantization volume, $|0\rangle$ represents the photon vacuum, and $\psi(\mathbf{p})$ is the momentum-space wave function (i.e., the amplitude associated with each electron momentum).

Within first-order perturbation theory, the final electron–photon state is described as $|f\rangle = \sum_{\mathbf{p}', \mathbf{k}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{V}} \psi(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p}') |\mathbf{p}'\rangle \otimes |1_{\mathbf{k}}\rangle$, where the sum now includes the emitted photon wave vector \mathbf{k} . Here, $\psi(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p}')$ is the corresponding amplitude, and $|1_{\mathbf{k}}\rangle$ denotes a one-photon state. Due to energy conservation, all initial electron states that transition to the same final electron state [black dot in Fig. 6(a)] by the emission of a photon of fixed energy but arbitrary direction (red lines) must be distributed along an isoenergetic surface (black dashed curves). In Supplement 1, Section 11, we show that the reduced photon-density operator is $\rho_{\text{ph}} = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{\mathbf{p}'} \sum_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'} \psi(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p}') \psi^*(\mathbf{k}', \mathbf{p}') |1_{\mathbf{k}}\rangle \langle 1_{\mathbf{k}'}|$. Thus, the coherence of the photon emission is determined by the width of $\psi(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{p}')$, which is fundamentally tied to the initial electron wave function $\psi(\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p}' + \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{k})$ via Fermi's golden rule. A detailed calculation can be found in Supplement 1, Section 12.

The electron transition from the initial state to the final state is sketched by the red-yellow lines in Fig. 6(a). The purple ellipse denotes the coherent momentum range of the initial electron [i.e., the distribution region of $\psi(\mathbf{p})$]. Electron coherence is transferred to the emitted photons by the connecting lines. From momentum conservation $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p}' + \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{k}$, we know that the electron coherent momentum range $\Delta\mathbf{p}$ required for the Airy beam can be approximated by $\Delta\mathbf{p} = \Delta(\mathbf{g} + \mathbf{k})$. The value of $\Delta(\mathbf{g} + \mathbf{k})$ can be calculated from Eq. (2). In Fig. 6(b), we plotted the maximum difference of $g_x + k_x$ along the caustic line for different sample radii, thicknesses, and L/R ratios, establishing a criterium for the approximate electron coherent momentum range required to generate Airy beams. When such range is smaller than this criterium, the generated Airy beam extends over a shorter axial length.

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Data availability. All data needed to evaluate the conclusions in the paper are present in the paper and the supporting content. Additional data related to this paper may be requested from the authors.

Supplemental document. See Supplement 1 for supporting content.

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